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WMD's of INDIA

WEAPONS OF MEN'S DESTRUCTION

Vicious Feminists Agenda

AUTHOR: RUDOLPH D'SOUZA

Co-author: Raghav Tanaji

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This study Article / Report is based on Legal Journals, Indian Penal code, Code of Criminal Procedure of India, Valid Statistics from National Crime Bureau (NCRB), reference from other study reports, Media coverage or testimonials from the victims, and not collected as Women organizations collect from Fake statistics or cooked up sob stories which have no valid backing.

Summary: The term "Weapons of Men's destruction (WMD)" covers a broad range of tactics, false cases, violent acts committed by one member of a family or household against another, especially by women against her male partner by using Women centric laws of India. These laws are biased against men and specially designed only for women and favor only young women, misuse of these laws Supreme Court of India called LEGAL TERRORISM.

As per National Crime Bureau (NCRB), reports and statistics almost 90% cases under various women centric laws end up dismissed / Quashed after man agree to pay hefty lumpsum. The exact numbers such cases are difficult to assess as majority cases go

MyNation Hope Foundation (INDIA)

Reg: S/1934/2018

Address: 133A, Pocket-C, Siddhartha Extn. New Delhi - 110014.

Phone: +91-9972718212

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unreported, but it's even tougher to figure out just how many men are suffering abuse and face LEGAL TERRORISM. A big part of the reason is traditional gender roles in society and the stigma of the perceived weakness of any man who admits to falling victim to a woman.

Key Findings: Majority men are ashamed to come forward to report such abuse, misuse of law to terrorise them by their wives, as there are no laws or Authorities like Police/Judge/Minister to report, reporting their abuse will be an Invitation to bigger trouble and charged with false cases like Section 498A of Indian Penal Code / Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act, 2005 these are few out of many WMDs of India, that make's men to suffer in silence.

Methodology: Information for this report was sourced from various secondary sources, all listed in the Reference List. Data from NCRB and various News publications and testimonies, Survey statistics of victims of Domestic violence also proved valuable. This report is not a comprehensive review of the available literature but provides a broad overview of the topic. It is an effort to highlight the plight of Men who are neglected by World Organizations and Government bodies. Even none of the survey data study Institutes or Media is not ready to publish misuse of law/Abuse on Men.

Introduction: MyNation analysis of statistics on Weapons of Men's Destructions shows the number of men not only terrorized by various India's Women centric laws but attacked/abused/harassed/killed by wives and girlfriends is much higher than ever thought. In India it's often assumed as women as victim and men as perpetrator/abuser, but the evidence collected by MyNation demonstrates that this is a false predomination, promoted by feminists and women organizations. Because there are dozens of one sided laws only for Women and None for Men

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Some time back, United States of America was on the lookout for weapons of mass destruction (WMD) in Iraq, which it assumed, the country may use on itself or on its allies. These WMD can destroy all life instantly. But the American military did not find any so called WMD in Iraq. Well, in reality, these WMDs are not in Iraq but in INDIA. These are called Weapons of Men Destruction.

You may wonder which these Indian WMDs are.

1st Place goes to **IPC 498A** (DP3) also known as Dowry Law: Under this law, one word by a wife is enough to land husband in jail without any formal investigation. She can name anyone along with her husband, like his old parents, brothers, sisters, friends, neighbors, relatives and even servants. There are many news reports of even police arresting a 4 month old breast feeding baby under this law. Any daughter in law can file a false case and there is no punishment for filling false cases and burden of showing proof lies on men. Police, Judges and Lawyers knows about this misuse, but for them it is a money making opportunity and these cases go on for not less than 5 years minimum. These Police and Lawyers suck men blood by harassing them ruin their career, and if man is in a government job he will lose his job as its criminal case, non bailable and non-compoundable. Under this Act, there is a 5 year punishment for giving dowry, but to date, no women or her family has been arrested for giving dowry. They report the case, only when the marriage is sore and on the brink of divorce. This Law was enacted in 1984.

2nd Place goes to **Domestic Violence Act** (PWDVA), this was enacted in 2006. Under this Law, daughter in law can file case on any male member of husband family, saying she was harassed mentally and physically. We have proof that some women have even filed a case just because she was asked to make tea for her husband and his friends. Under this law she can name any male members or husband's friends even if she has never met or seen them before and the police will take action on them. Burden of proof lies on men. In today's world, cooking and cleaning is considered to be harassment for women and today, most of the women do not know how to cook. Some have never been to the kitchen or do not even know where the kitchen is. They think their husband is a FREE ATM machine and he has to pay all her bills. That is his responsibility and he has no right to question what she is doing, where or with whom she is going and if questioned or the flow of money is reduced will be resulted in domestic violence false case.

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3rd Place goes to **Maintenance** (HMA). If man wants a Divorce, then he has to maintain his wife, that's Law; but In India, even if a women runs away with her lover or she want out of marriage siting some above False cases, the court will force the man to pay her. Most of the time, courts do not verify whether a man is capable to pay as much as women demand or he has that much source of income or not. There are judgments even on unemployed men; the court imposes maintenance by force. In one of Bombay HC case, the court forced the man to pay for the illegitimate child too. Here the women are not wrong to have illegitimate child, but if a man stop his wife from meeting her lover that leads to harassment. One Gujarat judgment says married women have the right to enjoy life outside marriage.

Divorce: women can file a case for divorce siting any of above false cases or, even when she gets caught red handed with her lover, she can blame husband for this situation. With Divorce, she will get add-on package as interim maintenance and the man has to pay her for no fault of his. She will get divorce within a year. But for men, there are limited options for divorce, he has no supporting laws to file false cases as above, even if his wife has run away with her lover and to prove that she will not come back, he has to wait for 7 years.

Child Custody: Out of 10,000 custody cases only 1 or 2 fathers get his custody of his child. The law says the father is a natural guardian; well that's only in the law books. In reality, he never gets custody of his child. If women is a prostitute or has deserted her child and goes abroad, she will get custody of her child by default. Till the age of 5, even the father has no right to ask for his child custody, but he has to pay for the child support only. This law is designed to make money for women from her husband, so the law gives her default custody till the child is 5 years, so women can raise her child and brainwash the child to hate his / her Father.

Outraging modesty (354 IPC): any women can file a case on any man for no reason and men are arrested without any formal investigation. Burden of proof lies on men, but if a woman does the same thing, a man has no supporting laws to protect him.

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Above are already existing WMDs, but there are many more in NCW / WCD menu.

Marital Rape: A wife can have consensual sex with her husband and the next day, she can report it to the police that she was raped by him.

Marital Cruelty: Promising a women to marry her later and then get married to someone else, leads to cruelty to her. But if a woman does the same to a man, that's not a cruelty to him.

Sexual Harassment at work Place: If a male employee shows or tells something which is even work related to a woman, she can report it to the police as sexual harassment for her. Man should not show that she is wrong, or if a female employee does not like some male employee, she can file a case against him simply to harass him and the burden of proof lies on men. Recently a women army major filed a case on her seniors, later she was proved wrong, but she did not have to compensate them for a year of false accusation or punishment for filing a false case.

Muslim Women Protection Bill: which became law on 31st July 2019 - one more addition to the arsenal of Weapon of Men destruction in India. This regressive act made to put Men behind bars (specifically Muslim) for 3 years in spite the Apex court in Shayara Bano case (2017) declared Triple Talaq unconstitutional. This law already proved its effectiveness by throwing many men into prisons on short notice of disgruntled wife. There are reports that many women are misusing this as a shield and take revenge when marriage is on the brink of divorce, even there was no word of talaq issued 3 times, but for men it's difficult to prove they have not called for any Triple Talaq but Women word is taken as Gospel Truth.

Accusation: In various accusation men and women file accusations to each other, in family related matters mostly Divorce / maintenance / Custody most of the time court hardly verify these minor accusations. In divorce cases, women can state in her petition to

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make her case stronger, that her husband was having affair, even if in reality, she was caught red handed having an extra marital affair. For women, no proof is required to write anything, but if man says something, it is regarded as harassment to her and NCW demands punishment for such accusation.

LIST OF SOME other Laws (CRIMINAL) Misused by Indian WOMEN

MISCARRIAGE

Causing Miscarriage 312 IPC Non Cognizable 3 to 7 yrs.

Causing Miscarriage without consent 313 IPC Cognizable. Life or 10 yrs.

Death caused while causing miscarriage without Woman's Consent 314 IPC Cognizable. 10 yrs. or Life

Act done to prevent child being born alive or to cause it to be after birth 315 IPC Cognizable 10 yrs.

KIDNAPPING

Kidnapping 363 IPC Cognizable. 7 yrs.

Kidnapping women to compel marriage, seduced to illicit inter course, etc. 366 IPC Cognizable. 10 yrs.

Procuration of minor girl under 18 years 366-A IPC Cognizable. 10 yrs.

Importation of girl 366-B IPC Cognizable. 10 yrs.

SEXUAL ASSAULT

Punishment for Rape or Life time 376 IPC Cognizable 7 to 10 yrs.

Intercourse by a man with him during Separation 376-A IPC Cognizable 2 yrs. & Fine

Intercourse by public servant with woman in his custody 376-B IPC Cognizable 5 yrs. & Fine

Intercourse by Superintendent of jail, remand home, etc. 376-C IPC Cognizable 5 yrs. & Fine

Intercourse by any member of the management or staff of a hospital with any woman in that hospital 376-D IPC Cognizable 5 yrs. & Fine

Unnatural Offences-carnal intercourse 377 IPC Cognizable Life or 10 yrs.

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MARRIAGE

Cohabitation caused by deceitfully inducing her under belief of lawful marriage 493 IPC Non-Cognizable 10 yrs.

Marrying again during life time of wife (away for 7 yrs.) 494 IPC Cognizable 7 yrs.

Going through unlawful marriage ceremony 496 IPC Cognizable 7 yrs.

Enticing, detaining a during women with criminal intention 498 IPC Cognizable 2 yrs.

CRUELTY

Abetment of suicide 306 IPC Cognizable 10 yrs. & Fine

Cruelty by Husband or Relatives-Mental or physical 498 A IPC Cognizable 3 yrs.

Uses indecent language or behaves in a disorderly committed in manner in a public street the Presence or public place of police (KP Act - Karnataka Police Act) 92 -(o)- K.P.Act Cognizable if Fine of Rs.100

Uses in any street abusive or insulting words or affixes or exhibits any indecent, threatening abusive or insulting paper or drawing with intent to provoke 92 -(r)-K.P.Act - do- -do5

MODESTY

Outraging modesty, use of criminal force with intention to outrage her modesty 354 IPC Cognizable 2 yrs.

Outraging modesty by Uttering gesture, sound 509 IPC Cognizable 1 yrs.

DOWRY HARASMENT

Dowry Death: 304-B-IPC Cognizable 7 yrs. to Life

A woman is caused by otherwise than normal circumstances within 7 years of her marriage and it is shown that soon before the death she was subjected to cruelty or harassment by her husband or relative for, or in connection with, any demand for dowry) Penalty for giving or taking Dowry (D.P.Act) 3 Dowry Prohibition Act. Cognizable 5 yrs. & Fine

Penalty for demanding Dowry (D.P.Act) Dowry Prohibition Act. Cognizable 6 months to 2 yrs. & Fine

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IMMORAL TRAFFIC

Punishment for living on the earnings of prostitution, Immoral Traffic (Prevention) Act Cognizable 2 yrs. or Fine or Both

Procuring inducing or taking woman or girl for the sake of prostitution Immoral Traffic (Prevent) Action Cognizable 3 to 7 yrs. & Fine

Detaining a woman or girl in premises where Action prostitution is carried on. Immoral Traffic (Prevent) Cognizable to 10 yrs. & Fine

Seduction of a woman or girl in custody Immoral Traffic (Prevent) Action Cognizable 7 yrs. or Life. & Fines

All above laws are misused widely, Women herself runaway with Boy then later claim she was kidnapped, Have sex and claim sexually harassed or raped and Burdon lies on men to prove her wrong and that take years, and even man says truth no one believe and women Lies all Believe in her. Man has to prove with Proofs and for women just word and some crocodile tears are enough.

These Laws are very cleverly drafted without leaving any option for man to prove women is wrong or sue if misused and sure slow Death.

Gender Arsenal is all about the uncalled for Gender War which has been initiated and is being fuelled by reasons outside the purview of this article. Gender Arsenal pertains to the weapons available to both the genders in the war. Before going into the actual details about the arsenal, I will elucidate the positions of the two genders vis-à-vis each other.

National Commission for Women (NCW) came into effect in 1992 in India to work on women's issues. NCW has been instrumental in making awareness about a lot of problems faced by women, and has recommended various legal and social options to redress them. It also looks into complaints received by women. Additionally women have around 3300 odd NGOs working for them, one union ministry and Rs. 26000 crores allocated for their cause annually from the union budget.

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But NO LAWS FOR MEN

I will now proceed to list down some laws meant specifically for women,

1. **Section 498A of the Indian Penal Code (IPC):** This section is formulated for married women who face physical and mental harassment from husband and in-laws and the cruelty is made for any unreasonable 'demand' (mostly dowry) from the woman and the cruelty is of such nature that it drives the woman to commit suicide or can be a danger to the life and limb of the woman.
2. **Section 354 of the IPC:** Assault or criminal force to woman with intent to outrage her modesty.
3. **Section 509 of the IPC:** Word, gesture or act intended to insult the modesty of a woman.
4. **Section 375 and 376 of the IPC:** Rape of a woman.
5. **Section 498 of the IPC:** Enticing or taking away or detaining with criminal intent a married woman
6. **Section 98 of the Criminal Procedure Code (CrPC):** Power to compel restoration of abducted females.
7. **Section 125 of the CrPC:** Meant to provide no-fault maintenance to wife from husband.
8. **Section 24 of the Hindu Marriage Act, 1955 (HMA):** Though gender neutral, is largely used by women to extract maintenance from their husbands in pendency of a divorce.
9. **Section 25 of the HMA:** Meant to provide alimony to women from divorce.
10. **Section 18 of the Hindu Adoptions and Maintenance Act:** Another provision for maintenance to wives.
11. **Dowry Prohibition Act, 1961:** Though gender neutral in its definition, this Act is largely used to protect women and there are also some judgments for cases filed under this Act, which are gender biased towards women.
12. **Immortal Trafficking Prevention Act:** Deals with trafficking of women.
13. **Indecent Representation of Women Act:** Title is self-explanatory.

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14. **Medical Termination of Pregnancy Act:** Empowers women to abort their unborn children legally.

15. **Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act:** Meant to tackle Domestic Violence faced by women.

These are some of the laws and Acts made to protect and empower women true to the best of my knowledge; I might have missed a few of them. However, these are only illustrative and not exhaustive of the fact that women are not only over-protected but pampered in this so called **Male Dominated Society**, whereas men do not have even a single NGO funded by the Govt. of India to be fighting for men's cause let alone any law, section, Act or a commission or a ministry.

It should give a fairly clear idea as to how unequally men and women are placed in this gender war wherein actually men are dragged into uncalled for. On one hand, where women have weapons to the tune of AK47 to their kitty as their arsenal, men do not even have nothing at their disposal.

And, as I said, the list is merely illustrative and not exhaustive; NCW has in its offing more laws to castrate men, some of them being,

1. Proposal for compensation of Rs. 2 Lakhs to rape victims.
2. Sexual Harassment Bill.
3. Workplace Harassment Bill.
4. Law to protect maids and so on and so forth.
5. Marital Rape.(Proposed)
6. 50% husband Property rights to women on marriage.

Again the list of prospective laws is also true to the best of my knowledge and I might have missed many others in the offing.

Whilst there are neither any laws existing to protect men, nor in the offing, and the simple reason for this is, men do not fight for their right or stand up for other men who are fighting for men's rights.

And if things continue this way, the day won't be far when NCW will come up with a law like this one:

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Inherent Protection of a Woman's Dream Act: Any woman, who complains against a man that the man entered her dreams and molested her/outraged her modesty/raped her, shall be tried with a relevant section of the IPC. Any married woman who complains against her husband and in-laws that they entered her dreams and demanded dowry from her or harassed her and assaulted her for not bringing enough dowry shall be charged with IPC Section 498A/Dowry Prohibition Act/Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act etc.

Choice lies with men; they can allow more and more such laws to be passed by not supporting men's rights or take a stand against all such laws and pressurize the Government to rethink about the laws.

Most of these WMDs are proposed and designed by NCW (National Commission for women) and WCD (Ministry for Women and Child development) with one goal in mind i.e. to harass and blackmail men and ruin their careers and financial positions, so they cannot lead a happy life and die inch by inch every day. These Indian WMDs are worse than the so called Iraqi WMDs because WMDs of Iraq can kill people instantly but these Indian WMDs are meant for slow death of Men. These WMDs will not kill Indian Men, but drain him of all his Money / assets, ruin his future and dreams. All this women can do with the blessings of National Commission for women (NCW) and support from the Government of India which turn blind eye on the suffering of Men.

Reference :

Domestic Violence: The Male Struggle to Survive and Mental Health

(<https://mynation.net/voice/ssrn-3665274>)

**LEGAL TERRORISM IN MATRIMONIAL DISPUTES - SOLUTION FOR
LEGAL TERRORISM** (<https://mynation.net/voice/ssrn-3695617>)

**VIOLENCE AGAINST MEN - FALSE ACCUSATION OF SEXUAL
HARASSMENT** (<https://mynation.net/voice/ssrn-3673754>)

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